

DEC↑S↓ION

Some Decision Cases

CASE

You have just learnt that a product that your company had sent to a small customer did not fully comply with the requirements. The customer has not detected this yet and may never do so. If you ignore this you can collect the payment immediately. However if it is found out, you could be sued. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Cover up the matter
- b) Recall the Product

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	+5000	-	+1
b	-1200	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-01

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A new business deal requires producing a quality certificate which you do not possess. You can easily fake the certificate, however there is a chance that you may be caught and be black-listed. The deal is extremely lucrative, and you are sure to win it if you can produce the certificate. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Fake the certificate & close the deal
- b) Invest in certification
- c) Pass the deal

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	+12000	-	+2
b	-1000	+1	-
c	0	-	-

DEC **ON**

1-02

Some Decision Cases

CASE

You have been approached by a leading agency who suggest a comprehensive branding program for your company. Your experience in the past has taught you that that branding is likely to have almost no impact on immediate sales. Many of your competitors are increasingly spending money on branding, but are yet to see direct benefits. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Go ahead with the branding
- b) Pass the opportunity for now

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-1200	+1	-
c	0	-	-

DEC **ON**

1-03

Some Decision Cases

CASE

Your company has been working on a new product development project for several years. You have been championing this project and have already poured 90,000 M on it. Your R&D team tells that the project will come through with another round of funding. However there is also a risk that the product will flop in the market. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Continue funding the project
- b) Scrap the project

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-1000	+1	+1
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-04

Some Decision Cases

CASE

An new employee has made an unwise delivery commitment to a customer that your company could not keep. You feel that firing the employee will send a positive signal and help retain the client, however this will severely demoralize employees. If nothing is done this could lead to similar incidents in the future. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Fire the employee
- b) Counsel & provide additional training
- c) Ignore the episode

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	+1	+2
b	-2000	-	-1
c	0	-	+1

DEC **ON**

1-05

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A company EFG which is the leader in its field is willing to pay you a large sum of money to contract manufacture for them. You see a possible loss in your ability to deliver other products and consequently reduced sales. However EFG is willing to help you improve your process, and this will reduce your risks. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Agree to the contract
- b) Opt out

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	20000	-2	-1
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-06

Some Decision Cases

CASE

Your star salesman, Mr K has always exceeded his targets and is the single most important reason for your recent success.. However there have been complaints of him misbehaving with subordinates. You have investigated the case, and have found it to be true. Even though he has been warned in the past, complaints continue. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Ask Mr K to leave
- b) Pay off the complainants
- c) Postpone the decision

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	-1	-2
b	-2000	-	0
c	0	-	+1

DEC↑**S**↓**ON**

1-07

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A large percentage of your sales come from a single client. They have been making increasingly unreasonable demands on you, and now want you to stop supplying your products to other clients. They are also not willing to negotiate. If you don't accept their demands, you will likely lose the client.. However, if you continue with them you increase your risks considerably. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Reject Demand
- b) Accept Demand

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	-2	-
b	0	-	+2

DEC↑**S**↓**ON**

1-08

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A company TUV has required you to produce a custom made sample of your product for evaluation. Just before dispatching it, you realize that the product has a flaw. The flaw is serious, but there is only a small chance it will be detected. If detected you are likely to lose the order and also harm your reputation. If not, you will very likely win a major order. You do not have time to re-design. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Dispatch the product
- b) Don't dispatch the product

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-500	+2	+1
b	0	-	-

DEC↑**S**↓**ON**

1-09

Some Decision Cases

CASE

Mr PQRS, the R&D head of your company is demanding a large one-time bonus. He is not willing to negotiate on the figure, and will leave if the full amount is not given. PQRS is a critical resource, and his departure will adversely impact the company sales and increase its risks. However, his departure will reduce costs as he is the most highly paid employee of the company. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Don't give the Bonus
- b) Give the Bonus

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	1000	-2	+1
b	-5000	+1	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-10

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A company JKL has approached you for the purchase of your most important patent, a technology which makes your product safer and stronger. After the sale, you will not be allowed to use the technology in your products. This will reduce your profits and increase your risks. However the price that JKL is willing to pay meets your previous valuation of your patent. You also feel that you could invest in more R&D with the money. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Sell the patent
- b) Don't sell the patent

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	25000	-2	+2
b	0	-	-

DEC↑**S**↓**ON**

1-11

Some Decision Cases

CASE

You have a single vendor MNO for a key component. Your analysis reveals that MNO is on the verge of bankruptcy. You have been considering looking for alternatives to reduce your risks. However change of vendors at this point can reduce your profits. MNO approaches you and says that they are willing to give you a large sum in down payment if you sign a long term contract with them. MNO says that this contract will help them survive. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Replace MNO with a new vendor
- b) Pen a long term contract with MNO

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	-1	-1
b	+20000	-	+2

DEC↑S↓ON

1-12

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A client PQR has paid full advance money to you to develop a product. You have completely spent the money on development and the product is not yet ready. To keep the project going for some more time you have to allocate key resources from other R&D projects. This in turn could reduce your market share. If you stop the development now, you have to return the entire advance paid immediately. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Continue the project
- b) Stop the project and return the advance

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	-1	+2
b	-10000	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-13

Some Decision Cases

CASE

Your Quality Head has suggested setting up a innovative new quality system that could significantly reduce product failures and warranty costs. This could however increase your cost and reduce your market-share. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Set up the new quality system
- b) Do not set up the new quality system

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-1000	-2	-2
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-14

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A large company in the territory has approached you directly for a deal. This order will be the biggest in your history. A company XYZ is your exclusive dealer in a certain territory. However, your profits will be substantially reduced if you involve XYZ in the deal. You can circumvent XYZ and take the deal directly, but this could hurt your reputation and make finding new dealers more difficult. You should take one of the below decisions

- a) Take the order through the dealer
- b) Take the order directly

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	+20000	-1	+1
b	+5000	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-15

Some Decision Cases

CASE

You have the option of buying a small R&D firm DEF. Your analysis shows that DEF is an attractive proposition, with several key patents to its name. The technology know-how at DEF will allow you to develop new products and also improve the quality of your existing products. However buying DEF will seriously crunch your financial resources. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Buy DEF
- b) Pass up the opportunity

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-20000	+2	-2
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-16

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A company PQR is willing to pay a large one-time sum to license a patented technology from your company. The competitor assures you that the technology will not be used in a competing product. The money from the sale will come in handy for your company and can be used for further R&D, however you feel that a licensing deal could reduce sales of all your products that use this technology. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) License the technology to PQR
- b) Do not license

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	+10000	-1	-
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-17

Some Decision Cases

CASE

You have discovered that the former CEO of your company has wrongly represented accounting information to reduce payable taxes. If this is detected your company will be penalized. You can set this right, pay up the dues and reduce your risks. However your chief accountant advises you against it, saying that this is unnecessary and that the liability will not be detected. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Pay up the dues
- b) Ignore the issue

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-5000	-	-1
b	0	-	+1

DEC↑S↓ON

1-18

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A leading insurance company has offered to cover certain of your business risks. The fee is hefty, but will substantially reduce your possible losses. The Chairman of the company feels that it is a good idea to go for insurance but wants you to come to a conclusion independently. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Take the insurance cover
- b) Don't take the insurance cover

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-15000	-	-2
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-19

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A leading global company MNO is seeking to partner with you in your country. This partnership can improve your sales and reduce your costs. MNO's cause is strongly championed by a junior manager in your company. This manager was previously employed with MNO and you feel that his opinion may be strongly biased. There is also a significant upfront investment required from your company to seal the partnership. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Partner with MNO
- b) Do not partner with MNO

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-10000	+1	-1
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-20

Some Decision Cases

CASE

A ex-employee of your competitor JKL has approached you and has offered you documents containing details of a patented technology of your competitor. You know that if you incorporate this technology in your products, it will fetch you a lucrative deal immediately. It will also increase your market share in the long term. However if JKL finds out, they will sue. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Accept the offer
- b) Reject the offer

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	+5000	+2	+2
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-21

Some Decision Cases

CASE

An innovative new product from your company is ready for launch. You are sure that the product will do extremely well in all the segments. Your market research team disagrees, and wants a pilot run first. This will eliminate the risk of the product doing poorly in some segments. You know that a pilot run, will allow your competitors to catch-up and reduce your sales. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Run a pilot
- b) Launch product immediately

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	+2	-1
b	-1000	+1	-

DEC↑**S**↓**ON**

1-22

Some Decision Cases

CASE

The marketing department suggests that your company should organize a series of exhibitions around the world to showcase your new products. They cite market research which show that the exhibitions could improve product sales significantly in several territories. However, your CFO also feels that it will be a waste of money, and is opposed to it. A similar suggestion was made last year, and you rejected it. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Organize the exhibitions
- b) Reject the suggestion

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	-10000	+2	-
b	0	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-23

Some Decision Cases

CASE

You have recently purchased one of your component vendors PQR. This purchase will help you decrease your costs and improve your product quality. Now, the former owners of PQR have approached you to buy back the company for a steep premium. Your CFO is in favor of the sale as you would have made a neat profit in the resulting exchange. You should take one of the below decisions.

- a) Sell back PQR to the owners
- b) Do not sell back PQR

Decision	Cash Flow	G	L
a	0	+1	-2
b	+5000	-	-

DEC↑S↓ON

1-24

Some Decision Cases

DECISION MAKING

Ethical Decision Making

Sunk Cost & Escalation of Commitment

Emotional Decision Making

Confirmation Bias

Wishful Thinking

Anchoring